

PUMPING STATION AS AN EFFECTIVE FLOOD CONTROL PROJECT OF VALENZUELA CITY

**John A. Cabaddu; Shekinah Remila V. Acuña; Jonnalyn A. Carcha;
Danica P. Colandog; Ericka Mae A. Gonzales; Elsly Carlene G. Tan**

Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Valenzuela

Abstract

Flooding affects several low-lying regions in Metro Manila, such as Valenzuela City, and is usually among the worst hit in every series of flooding. Hence, certain low-lying areas are still exposed and deal with flooding. These flooding situations turned into a significant turning point in the Philippine government's commitment to flood control. The pumping station is one such initiative, aimed at mitigating flooding and managing water waste. Thus, this study aims to evaluate the functionality in reducing the frequency, intensity, and contribution to enhancing urban flood resilience. Moreover, this paper employs a mixed-method approach to gain in-depth understanding, knowledge and strengthen the reliability and validity of the information and data gathered. This approach provides comprehensive data that Local Government Units (LGUs) can use to develop the project further. Based on the study, the researchers found out that the pumping stations are very effective flood control project since they will quickly alleviate flooding in a short period of time and continuously operate even when it is not raining. Additionally, the pumping station has the potential to enhance residence safety, beginning with the local government and continuing up to the national level, as long as it continues to manage solid waste since waste can cause malfunction in the pumping station. Concerning this, it is important to establish a policy and program recommendation designed to strengthen the operations of pumping station projects in Valenzuela City.

Keywords – Flooding, Flood Control, Flood Mitigation, Local Government Units (LGUs), Metro Manila, Pumping Stations, Philippines, Urban Flood Resilience, Valenzuela City

INTRODUCTION

Flooding is one of the issues that people throughout the world are facing. The Philippines is at high risk of natural disasters caused by climate change that prompts typhoons and floods. There are an average of 20 cyclones every year, which causes flooding to be the major problem in the country (Pagasa, 2023). Flooding is a natural phenomenon in the Philippines due to the proximity between communities and water bodies. Flooding remains a problem in the Philippines despite flood control programs put in place by the Philippine government, and it poses risks to the increasing population, especially in urban areas, due to climate change (Rinen, 2022). As a compliance measure, the city government of Valenzuela took some actions to mitigate flooding in low-lying areas. Valenzuela City, in the Philippines is flood-prone and susceptible to such extreme flooding as may come from natural causes like typhoons. Nearly 1/3 of the city is swampy due to being on fishponds while also being a typhoon belt area, which causes flooding affecting multiple barangays under its jurisdiction (Cities Development Initiative for Asia, 2020). This research focuses on Valenzuela City's flood control projects with the support of the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH).

Meanwhile, despite the establishment of pumping stations that are strategically located in flood-prone regions, severe flooding continues to impact communities. Certain low-lying areas remain exposed to flooding, which indicates inadequacy of the current flood control. The study by Wang et al. (2022) shows that flood control has lapses and is unable to cope with today's flood situations. Therefore, it is essential to evaluate how effective the pumping stations are in Valenzuela City.

To fill the gap, the objective of this study is to understand the personal experience and response of the residents towards the flood and determine the effectiveness of a pumping station in reducing the frequency and severity of floods in Valenzuela City, additionally as to identify the problems and challenges faced in its implementation. The result is being used in development of the program to improve the implementation of a pumping station, which is crucial for achieving the Sustainable Development Goal of 2030. Pumping stations are an example of innovative and resilient infrastructure that contributes to a sustainable way of life. Along with SDG 9, this is also anchored in SGD 13, or climate action since this infrastructure is another tool to combat climate change by protecting communities from natural disasters.

This research aims to determine the effectiveness of Valenzuela City's pumping stations as their flood control project in terms of decreasing the frequency and intensity of floods. This study evaluated the impact of pumping stations on the positive community development, urban flood resilience, and local government flood control programs through decision-making and strategic infrastructure development.

Moreover, the findings of the study can also benefit the local government units (LGUs) in enhancing the flood resilience of the community. This may empower policymakers about the importance of establishing pumping stations for flood control projects and contributes to public administration by improving leadership and decision-making processes. Thus, the main goal of this paper is to investigate the effectiveness of pumping stations in Valenzuela City by assessing their experiences. In the end, this paper makes recommendations to improve pumping stations in Valenzuela City. To achieve this goal, data from different local governments, such as the Flood Control Division and the operators of the pumping stations, were assessed and analyzed.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers used a mixed-method approach that combined both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques. It involved triangulation to strengthen the reliability and validity of the information and data that had been gathered. The study evaluated pumping stations in 360 residents of Brgy. Wawang Pulo and Coloong for flood mitigation in Valenzuela City assessing. Quantitative data was analyzed through structured surveys, while qualitative data was collected through open-ended questionnaires and semi-structured interviews are the key informants to acquire an in-depth understanding and additional data. Additionally, this study is designed to thoroughly evaluate the effectiveness of pumping stations as flood control measures within Valenzuela City by answering the three key research questions: (1) What are the experiences of the residents of Valenzuela City towards flood? (2) How effective is the establishment of a pumping station in controlling floods? (3) What are the problems and challenges identified in the implementation of a pumping stations in Valenzuela City? This paper examined an in-depth exploration of personal experiences among residents of flood-prone areas to answer the first research question. To answer the second research question, the researchers used survey questionnaire and interview to gather a comprehensive information, on the operational performance of pumping stations through survey questionnaire and interview among residents and supplemented with key informants' or expert insights from Flood Control Division and head operator of the pumping station. For the third research question, the detailed information was gathered from both residents and key informants who are involved in the operation of pumping stations ensure the reliability of the information. In order to

achieve the study's overall goal, the data were analyzed and explained using thematic analysis through existing literature such as published researches, journals, articles, government policies, and reports.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

I. Experiences of the residents of Valenzuela City towards flood

Flooding is a natural phenomenon in the Philippines, particularly in third-world cities like Metro Manila, where areas such as Pasig Marikina River basin, West Mangahan, and Caloocan, Malabon, Navotas, and Valenzuela (CAMANAVA) areas are especially vulnerable due to low-lying coastal areas and weak drainage infrastructure (Porio, 2011). According to 360 surveyed residents in Barangay Coloong and Wawang Pulo, Valenzuela City, all of them claimed that before the establishment of the pumping station, they all experienced flooding and most of them stated that the depth of flood is chest level at 34.63%. Water depth is considered as the most informative proxy variable for assessing the impact in flooding due to its direct correlation with the severity of flooding. With the increase of floodwaters, the damage it will cause to households and the environment also increases (Betterle & Salamon, 2024). However, 303 respondents mentioned that even after the pumping station was established, they are still experiencing flood. Since the establishment of the pumping station, the depth of flooding has decreased. Most respondents report that they are now only experiencing flooding at the gutter level, with 25.74% indicating this situation. Regarding this, areas with improved drainage systems and pumping stations, such as those under the Metro Manila Flood Management Project, have experienced significant reductions in flood depth (World Bank Group, 2017).

Moreover, the floods the residents experienced during rainfall have decreased to 3.96% due to the construction of the pumping station in Valenzuela City. However, most residents report that flooding still mainly occurs during typhoons, and this situation has not changed significantly since the flood control measures were implemented. This is because the Philippines is considered as the fourth most vulnerable to extreme weather conditions including typhoons and flash floods throughout the world (Eckstein, 2021).

Further, the residents experience flooding for more than five days (50%) before a pumping station is installed in their area. This prolonged flooding significantly impacts their daily lives, affecting their work (21.65%) and making it difficult to obtain basic commodities (14.49%). Nevertheless, 35.64% of the respondents stated that the flood receded faster less than an hour after the pumping station was established. In line with this, the flooding only affects transportation (32.68%). Rebally et al. (2021) highlighted that flooding can impact transportation networks both immediately and over time by causing delays, damaging infrastructure, and prolonging recovery efforts, which may also have economic consequences. In terms of the residents' defense in their property, before and after the pumping station was established, they only had a home drainage system. As Sohn et al. (2020) emphasized, these properly planned drainage systems effectively provide efficient stormwater discharge and lower property damage and recovery costs. This effectiveness can mitigate floods and reduce property destruction.

Table 1: The Experiences of Residents in Flooding Before and After the Establishment of the Pumping Station

STATEMENT	BEFORE		AFTER	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. I believe that my neighborhood is at high risk of flooding.	4.47	Strongly agree	2.46	Disagree
2. I feel safe in my home during heavy rainfall and potential flooding.	2.52	Disagree	3.77	Agree
3. I have a plan in place for what to do in case of a flood.	3.67	Agree	3.31	Neutral
4. I have had to evacuate my home due to flooding in the past.	3.76	Agree	1.95	Disagree
5. I must move household items to higher places due to feet deep of flooding.	3.95	Agree	1.91	Disagree
6. My house was damaged due to strong typhoons and flooding.	3.00	Neutral	1.68	Strongly Disagree
7. I find it difficult to buy what we need when there is a flood.	4.12	Agree	2.42	Disagree
8. My family suffered financial deficiency because of the flood.	4.18	Agree	2.51	Disagree
9. I experienced electricity and water interruption due to typhoons and severe flooding.	4.28	Strongly Agree	2.73	Neutral
Average Weighted Mean	3.77	Agree	2.53	Dis-agree

Furthermore, the overall assessment of the residents in flooding before and after the establishment of pumping stations, shows that the average weighted mean 3.77 has been reduced significantly to 2.53. An indication of significant improvement of the residents' experiences at Barangay Coloong and Wawang Pulo and thus shows that it enhances quality of life in the entire community as well as it is beneficial to them to have pumping stations within their areas. This is in line with the findings of Pramono et al. (2023) who emphasized that the objective of the pumping station is to solve the flood problems. It indicates that the pumping station has succeeded in addressing and alleviating the flood problem faced by the community.

II. Effectiveness of Pumping Stations as Flood Control

In this study, the results from the Likert scale section of the survey indicate the effectiveness of a pumping station in Valenzuela City in controlling floods. The table below presents the statements provided to respondents, along with their computed weighted mean and corresponding verbal interpretations. This information helps to assess the performance of the pumping stations. Each statement is rated on a scale, and the overall weighted mean is calculated to evaluate how well the stations address flood issues and serve the community at large.

Table 2: The Effectiveness of Establishment of a Pumping Station in Controlling Floods

STATEMENT	WM	VI
1. The establishment of a pumping station prevents flooding in the community.	4.38	Very Effective
2. The establishment of pumping stations lessened the number of flood cases in different areas of the barangay.	4.36	Very Effective
3. I rely on a pumping station when there is a typhoon or heavy rain for mitigating and managing floods.	4.30	Very Effective
4. I am confident in the ability of pumping stations to prevent flooding during heavy rains or storms.	4.25	Very Effective
5. The establishment of a pumping station improves community resilience to flooding.	4.44	Very Effective

6. I observed improvements in flood control measures since the pumping stations were established.	4.26	Very Effective
7. The pumping station has operated efficiently for the past years.	4.12	Very Effective
8. The establishment of pumping stations have sufficient capacity to meet the demands of the community.	4.31	Very Effective
9. I am satisfied with the overall performance of the pumping stations in our area.	4.30	Very Effective
10. The establishment of the pumping station addresses the public's concerns and preferences regarding flood control.	4.34	Very Effective
11. Pumping stations play a crucial role in protecting the environment and decreasing environmental pollution.	4.33	Very Effective
Average Weighted Mean		4.31
		Very Effective

Flood Prevention and Mitigation

The respondents observed that since the pumping station was established, it helped to prevent flooding in the community. It was evident as it was exhibited by the weighted mean of 4.38 falling within the “Very Effective” response. Additionally, it lessened the number of flood cases in different areas of their barangay, with a weighted mean of 4.36 indicated as “Very Effective.” According to Choi et al. (2016) the operation of pumping stations helps to reduce water levels from flood damage. Flood control collects and removes water from low-lying areas during intense rainfall, protecting homes from water damage (Resolute Civils, 2024). Since Valenzuela City frequently suffers or experiences flooding every time there is a typhoon or heavy rain, that is why most of the residents rely on pumping stations for flood risk management. A weighted mean of 4.30, it classifies as “very effective.” Also, residents emphasize their trust in the capacity of the pumping station for flood defense with a weighted mean of 4.25, which falls within “Very Effective” response. An early operation of flood control is essential for reducing flood experience (Pandit, 2024).

Community Resilience and Adaptation

The pumping station enhances the community’s resilience to floods. According to Zhong (2020), community resilience as a crucial metric for understanding human habitat systems’ response to threats, emphasizing the need for indicators and quantitative measurements. The weighted mean of 4.44 indicates a unanimous response of “Very Effective,” reflecting a distinctly positive sentiment regarding the statement. Furthermore, the statement “I observed improvements in flood control measures since the pumping stations were established” received a weighted mean of 4.26, which also demonstrates a unanimous “Very Effective” response, underscoring the positive sentiments expressed.

Capacity and Efficiency of Pumping Stations

The statement expressed that the pumping station has operated efficiently for the past years since the operators always ensure that the water does not exceed the average standard height. According to Nevogt (2024), operational efficiency involves enhancing systems and procedures to produce the best benefits or outcome without sacrificing quality. The weighted mean of 4.12 underscores a unanimous “Effective” response. In addition, pumping stations have sufficient capacity to meet the demands of the community in terms of floods. As evidenced by a weighted mean of 4.33 underscores a unanimous “Very Effective” response, affirming a distinctly positive sentiment towards the statement.

Public Perception and Satisfaction

Pumping station is a government initiative for flood control and it is vital to ensure that it is effective in reducing floods experienced by the community. The positive sentiment expressed in the statement, “I am satisfied with the overall performance of the pumping stations in our area”, was evident by a weighted mean of 4.30 underscores a unanimous “Very Effective” response. It was supported by the study of Ganiron (2017), the pumping station in Quiapo and Binondo the City of Manila is effective in mitigating or alleviating flood problems. Also, the establishment of the pumping station addresses the public’s concerns and needs on flood control. Aggregate weighted mean of 4.34 clearly states a “Very Effective” response.

Environmental Benefits of Pumping Station

Most of the respondents emphasized that the pumping stations as flood control play a crucial role in protecting the environment and decreasing environmental pollution. It was evidenced by the weighted mean of 4.33, which falls within the “Very Effective” response category, affirming a distinctly positive sentiment towards the statement. By managing the water supply and wastewater, pumping stations keep rivers, lakes, and natural areas clean and preserve ecosystem balance (Resolute Civils, 2024).

III. The Problems and Challenges in the Implementation of Pumping Station in Valenzuela City

Pumping stations effectively reduced floods, but they face challenges and unintended consequences, affecting residents’ lives and well-being. The table below displayed some of the problems and issues identified by 360 respondents after the establishment of pumping stations.

Table 3: The Problems and Challenges that the Residents Noticed or Experienced Since the Pumping Stations were Established

	FREQUENCY	PER-CENTAGE	RANK
Noise generated by the machinery	116	15.06%	3
Flooding still occurs	93	12.08%	5
Water leakage	49	6.36%	7
Produces unpleasant odors	157	20.39%	2
Clogging of garbage	167	21.69%	1
Contamination of nearby water sources	56	7.27%	6
Increased presence of pests	100	12.99%	4
Difficulty sleeping at night due to bright lights	14	1.82%	8
Decrease in property quality	7	0.91%	10
<i>Others:</i>			
Always broken	9	1.17%	9

According to Ogie et al. (2017), pumping stations are more susceptible to failure due to waste blockage. In line with that, the data in this study revealed that the primary problem and challenge faced by pumping stations is the clogging of garbage, accounting for 21.69% of responses. In 2017, they also mentioned that coastal mega-cities face garbage blockage at pumping stations, leading to drainage system malfunctions. Inefficient resource allocation and inability to identify vulnerable stations can hinder preventive maintenance. This problem results in the page-emitting problem of unpleasant odors, affecting 20.39% of respondents, which is caused by stagnant water, garbage, or inefficient wastewater treatment processes, and can negatively impact the quality-of-life. Urban wastewater pumping stations are responsible for a huge amount of odour in the northern parts of China (Lu & Li, 2011).

Moreover, another problem was identified by 15.06% of respondents in the implementation of the pumping station; the noise generated by the machinery, hinder their daily activities. In addition, 12.99% of the respondents reported an increase in pests due to stagnant water and garbage that attract pests. As well as even with established pumping stations, flooding remains a problem among respondents, indicating 12.08%. Pumping stations have been established in Manila, but the city is not totally exempt from high floods (Ganiron, 2014).

The findings mean the need for improvement in the operation, maintenance, and environmental management of pumping stations to solve the problems of the community well. It shows that the intended benefits of these stations are compromised by various challenges related to maintenance, operation, and the environment, which reflect the urgency of managing or upgrading the infrastructural development of the pumping stations.

CONCLUSION

Flooding occurs in several low-lying areas in Metro Manila. This study found out that the flood experienced by residents was previously severe with a long duration before it subsided, which was solely due to heavy rains. The pumping stations in Barangay Coloong and Wawang Pulo have been highly effective in reducing the frequency and severity of floods after it was established in Valenzuela City. Additionally, it enhanced urban flood resilience and quality of life. However, despite these benefits, challenges persist and highlight the need for further enhancement of its operation and strong policies in terms of waste management. Therefore, while pumping stations have proven that is an effective flood control project, addressing its challenges will not only maximize the operation of these pumping stations but also, strengthen community flood resilience and improve waste management practices.

RECOMMENDATIONS

A key finding of the study is that one of the most effective solutions to mitigate flooding is proper waste disposal around pumping stations and throughout the city. This practice will help prevent blockages that can hinder their function. To achieve this, it will be necessary to establish clear, measurable goals that address both current issues and future needs, while also balancing expectations between the two. An intelligent planning process should be focused, as needed, on safety and well-being of the residents who live in areas subject to flooding. Noise reduction, unpleasant odor controls, and light pollution controls should be put in place to minimize disruption to the quality of life of residents in nearby areas. By investing in operator training and reliable monitoring systems, issues can be identified and rectified in a timely fashion, leading to an increased operational efficiency. Opening up federal funding for more maintenance and upgrades is essential to help the stations prepare for challenges posed by climate change and rapid urbanization. Community engagement investment will lead to informed and engaged residents to be involved in the process will enable them to participate in their community by being informed and engaged in any discussion on how the station can be operated and maintained. Pumping stations can play a vital role in supporting and enhancing flood control efforts in Valenzuela City and can contribute to better urban flood resilience by addressing these issues comprehensively to secure the overall well-being of the residents. This engagement will create a sense of community and trust, enabling residents to feel secure and empowered against potentially flooding threats.

REFERENCES

Betterle, A., & Salamon, P. (2024). Water depth estimate and flood extent enhancement for satellite-based inundation maps. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 24(8), 2817–2836. <https://nhess.copernicus.org/articles/24/2817/2024/>

- Choi, H. S., Kim, J. H., & Yazdi, J. (2016, June). A methodology for optimal operation of pumping stations in urban drainage systems. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jher.2015.09.001>
- Cities Development Initiative for Asia. (2020). Valenzuela integrated flood risk management. CDIA. <https://cdia.asia/project/valenzuela-integrated-flood-risk-management/>
- Eckstein, D., Künzel, V., & Schäfer, L. (2021, January 25). Global climate risk index 2021. German Watch. <https://www.germanwatch.org/en/19777>
- Ganiron Jr., T. U. (2017, October). Environment and Natural Resources: Pump Station Flooding Impact Assessment. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/300085226_Environment_and_Natural_Resources_Pump_Station_Flooding_Impact_Assessment
- Ganiron, T.U. (2014). An Analysis of the Public Perception of Floods in Manila City. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/An-Analysis-of-the-Public-Perception-of-Floods-in-Ganiron/f6d2a2b322cd2c8beadb13d-d716e46517bdb9611#cited-papers>
- Lu, R., & Li, M. (2011). Notice of Retraction Odorous Compounds Hazards and Health Risk Assessment of Urban Sewage Pumping Station. 2011 5th International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedical Engineering, 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICBBE.2011.5781235>.
- Nevogt, D. (2024, November 25). What is operational efficiency and how to measure it: A guide. Hubstaff Blog. <https://hubstaff.com/blog/operational-efficiency/>
- Ogie, R.I., Dunn, S., Holderness, T., & Turpin, E. (2017). Assessing the vulnerability of pumping stations to trash blockage in coastal mega-cities of developing nations. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 28, 53-66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCS.2016.08.022>
- Pagasa. (2023, September 30). <https://www.pagasa.dost.gov.ph/learning-tools/floods>
- Pandit, B. A. (2024, October 31). A concentrated analysis of the situation of flood control management: A review. Semantic Scholar | AI-Powered Research Tool. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/A-Concentrated-Analysis-of-the-Situation-of-Flood-A-Pandit/636625dc92774b1895faea9b533e46369e9f20>
- Porio, E. (2011). Vulnerability, Adaptation, and Resilience to Floods and Climate Change-Related Risks among Marginal, Riverine Communities in Metro Manila. *Asian Journal of Social Science*, 39, 425-445. https://brill.com/view/journals/ajss/39/4/article-p425_3.xml
- Pramono, S., Roekminiati, S., & Vitianingsih, A. V. V. (2023). Effectiveness of Flood Management Through Pump Houses Based on Geographic Information Systems in the City of Surabaya. Atlantis Press. Atlantis Press, 349-368. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-2-38476-082-4_32
- Rebally, A., Valeo, C., He, J., & Saidi, S. (2021). Flood Impact Assessments on Transportation Networks: A review of methods and associated temporal and spatial scales. *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsc.2021.732181>
- Resolute Civils. (2024, July 4). What is the purpose of a pumping station? <https://resolutecivils.com/purpose-of-pumping-station/>
- Rinen, R. M. (2022). Flood Control Projects in the Philippines: A Historical Overview. *MUHON: A Journal of Architecture, Landscape Architecture, and the Designed Environment*, 8(8). <https://journals.upd.edu.ph/index.php/muhon/article/view/8565>
- Sohn, W., Brody, S., Kim, J.-H., & Li, M.-H. (2020). How effective are drainage systems in mitigating flood losses? *Science Direct*, 107, 102917. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0264275120312658?via%3Dihub>
- Wang, L., Cui, S., Li, Y., Huang, H., Manandhar, B., Nitivattananon, V., Fang, X., & Huang, W. (2022, November). A review of the flood management: from flood control to flood resilience. *Cell Press*, 8(11). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11763>
- World Bank Group. (2017). Project Highlights: Metro Manila Flood Management. In World Bank. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/philippines/brief/project-highlights-metro-manila-flood-management>
- Zhong, M., Lin, K., Tang, G., Zhang, Q., Hong, Y., & Chen, X. (2020). A Framework to Evaluate Community Resilience to Urban Floods: A Case Study in Three Communities. *Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12041521>.